

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL ANTI- INFLAMMATORY GEL CONTAINING MORINGA OLEIFERA AND CURCUMA LONGA

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ABSTRACT

Herbal medicines are widely used for primary healthcare due to their natural origin, cultural acceptance, and minimal side effects. The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a polyherbal anti-inflammatory gel containing Moringa oleifera and curcumin extracts for topical drug delivery. Carbopol 934 and propylene glycol were used as the gel base and penetration enhancer. The prepared gel formulations were evaluated for parameters such as compatibility, viscosity, drug content, spreadability, swelling index, and stability. The formulations showed good consistency, optimum spreadability, stable behavior, and effective anti-inflammatory activity without causing skin irritation. The study concludes that the polyherbal gel may serve as a safe and effective topical treatment for inflammatory conditions.

KEYWORDS: Gel, Curcumin, Moringa, anti-inflammatory.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a protective biological response of the body against harmful stimuli such as pathogens, irritants, damaged cells, or toxic substances. It is characterized by redness, swelling, heat, pain, and loss of function. Although inflammation helps in tissue repair and healing, prolonged inflammation may lead to chronic diseases such as arthritis, cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, and skin diseases. Conventional anti-inflammatory drugs like NSAIDs and steroids are effective but may cause side effects such as gastric irritation, ulcers, and kidney damage during long-term use. Therefore, herbal medicines are gaining attention due to their safety, effectiveness, and fewer adverse effects.

Moringa oleifera is a well-known medicinal plant belonging to the family Moringaceae and is widely used in traditional medicine due to its therapeutic properties. The leaves, seeds, bark, and roots of Moringa contain various bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, and vitamins,

which contribute to its pharmacological activities. Moringa exhibits significant anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting the release of inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins, cytokines, cyclooxygenase (COX), and lipoxygenase (LOX) enzymes. It also possesses strong antioxidant properties that help reduce oxidative stress associated with inflammation. Due to these properties, Moringa oleifera is widely used in the treatment of pain, swelling, wounds, arthritis, and skin inflammation, making it a promising natural anti-inflammatory agent for herbal formulations.

Curcuma longa possesses strong anti-inflammatory activity mainly due to the presence of curcumin, its major active constituent. Curcumin inhibits inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins, cytokines, and enzymes like cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX). It also suppresses inflammatory pathways such as NF- κ B and exhibits antioxidant properties, which help reduce pain, swelling, and tissue inflammation. Therefore, Curcuma longa is widely used in herbal formulations for the treatment of wounds,

arthritis, and skin inflammation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS MORINGA OLEIFERA

fresh or dried leaves, seeds, roots, bark, and pods of the plant *Moringa oleifera* Lam.

Family: Moringaceae

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE OF MORINGA OLEIFERA: PROCEDURE

1. Extraction Process of *Moringa oleifera*
2. Collection of fresh *Moringa* leaves
3. Washing to remove dust and impurities
4. Shade drying at room temperature
5. Grinding dried leaves into coarse powder
6. Soaking powder in ethanol/methanol (maceration)
7. Keeping for 48–72 hours with occasional stirring
8. Filtration using muslin cloth or filter paper
9. Concentration of filtrate by solvent evaporation
10. Collection of semisolid extract
11. Storage in airtight container for further use

Synonym: Horseradish tree, Shigru and Drumstick tree

Biological Source: *Moringa oleifera* is obtained from the

PRIMARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF MORINGA OLEIFERA

Sr.No	Component	Test	Inference
1.	Alkaloids	Dragendorff's Test	Positive
2.	Flavonoids	Shinoda Test	Positive
3.	Tannins	Ferric Chloride Test	Positive
4.	Saponins	Foam Test	Positive
5.	Glycosides	Keller-Killiani Test	Positive
6.	Proteins	Biuret Test	Positive

CURCUMA LONGA

Synonym: Haldi, *Rhizoma Curcumae Longae*

Biological Source: The biological source of *Curcuma longa* is the dried and fresh rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* Linn., belonging to the family Zingiberaceae.

Family: Zingiberaceae

MACERATION PROCEDURE FOR CURCUMA LONGA

1. Collection of rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*
2. Cleaning, washing, and drying of rhizomes
3. Grinding into coarse or fine powder
4. Transfer of powdered drug into a closed container
5. Addition of suitable solvent (ethanol / methanol /

- water)
6. Soaking for 3–7 days with occasional stirring
 7. Filtration to separate liquid extract from marc (residue)
 8. Collection of filtrate (extract solution)
 9. Concentration of filtrate by evaporation or water bath
 10. Drying and storage of the final Curcuma extract

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF CURCUMA LONGA

Sr. No	Component	Test	Inference
1.	Alkaloids	Dragendorff's Test	Positive
2.	Flavonoids	Shinoda Test	Positive
3.	Tannins	Ferric Chloride Test	Positive
4.	Glycosides	Keller-Killiani Test	Positive
5.	Carbohydrates	Molisch's Test	Positive
6.	Test for Curcuminoid	Boric Acid Test	Positive

PROCEDURE FOR PREPARATION OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY GEL FORMULATION TABLE

Sr. No	Ingredient	(F3)	(F4)
1.	Moringa Oleifera Extract	1ml	1ml
2.	Curcuma longa extract	4ml	6ml
3.	Carbopol	2 gm	2 gm
4.	Polyethylene glycol	7.5ml	7.5ml
5.	Methyl paraben	0.9gm	0.9gm
6.	Propyl paraben	0.01gm	0.01gm
7.	Glycerine	2.5ml	2.5ml
8.	Triethanolamine	2ml	2ml
9.	Alcohol	7.5ml	7.5ml
10.	Rose Water	Q. S	Q. S
11.	Distilled Water	Q. S	Q. S

PROCEDURE

Step 1: Preparation of Carbopol Gel Base

Accurately weigh 2 g of Carbopol and disperse it slowly in a sufficient quantity of distilled water with continuous stirring to avoid lump formation.

Allow the dispersion to stand for about 24 hours for

complete hydration and swelling of Carbopol.

Step 2: Preparation of Preservative Solution

Dissolve 0.9 g methyl paraben and 0.01 g propyl paraben in 7.5 ml alcohol using gentle stirring.

Add 7.5 ml polyethylene glycol (PEG) and 2.5 ml

glycerine to the above solution and mix properly until a clear mixture is obtained.

Step 3: Incorporation of Herbal Extracts

Add 1 ml Moringa oleifera extract to the prepared mixture. Add Curcuma longa extracts according to formulation batches:

$$F3 = 4 \text{ ml } F4 = 6 \text{ ml}$$

Stir continuously to obtain a uniform herbal mixture.

Step 4: Preparation of Gel

Add the herbal mixture slowly into the hydrated Carbopol gel base with continuous stirring.

Add 2 ml triethanolamine dropwise to neutralize Carbopol and to form a smooth gel consistency.

Add rose water and sufficient quantity of distilled water (Q.S.) to obtain the desired final volume and consistency.

Step 5: Final Processing

Stir the formulation continuously until a homogeneous gel is formed. Remove entrapped air by keeping the gel

undisturbed for some time.

Transfer the prepared gel into a suitable airtight container and store at room temperature.

EVALUATION OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY GEL

The prepared gel was evaluated using a range of parameters in accordance with conventional protocols.

Physical Evaluation

In this test, the gel was observed for colour, odour, appearance, structure.

Sr. No	Parameters	Formulation (F3)	Formulation (F4)
1.	Colour	Yellow Green	Yellow Green
2.	Odour	Characteristic Herbal	Characteristic Herbal
3.	Appearance	Smooth	Smooth
4.	State	Semi- Solid	Semi- Solid

pH

The pH of the prepared formulation was measured using a digital pH Meter.

Sr. No	Formulation	pH
1.	Formulation	4.20
2.	Formulation	4.73
3.	Formulation	5.21

Spreadability

The spreadability was determined by placing sample between two glass slides which was compressed to

uniform thickness by applying definite time period.

Where, $S = L * M / T$

Sr. No	Formulation	Time(sec)	Spreadability
1.	Formulation (F3)	12	23.6
2.	Formulation (F4)	07	29.2
3.	Formulation (F5)	20	17.9

Consistency

Smooth and no greening is observed.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The polyherbal anti-inflammatory gel containing *Moringa oleifera* and *Curcuma longa* extracts was prepared successfully and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters. The formulation showed good appearance, homogeneity, stability, spreadability, extrudability, pH, viscosity, and drug content uniformity, indicating suitability for topical application. Good homogeneity and smooth consistency are essential for patient acceptability and uniform drug distribution. The prepared gel showed satisfactory aesthetic properties suitable for topical use. The following are the outcomes of the same.

PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

Alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, tannins, saponins, glycosides, terpenoids, steroids, carbohydrates, proteins, and amino acids were found to be present in the ethanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* according to phytochemical screening. The presence of these constituents was confirmed by Mayer's test, Shinoda test, ferric chloride test, foam test, Keller–Killiani test, Salkowski test, Molisch test, and Ninhydrin test, which showed positive result.

Phytochemical screening of *Curcuma longa* confirms the presence of curcuminoids, phenols, flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, and essential oils. These constituents are responsible for its medicinal and antioxidant properties.

Evaluation of Gel

Physical Evaluation

1. **Colour** – Yellow Green
2. **Odour** – characteristic Herbal
3. **Appearance** – Smooth
4. **State** – Semi-solid

pH

The pH of the formulated polyherbal gel was found to be

within the suitable skin pH range, indicating good compatibility for topical application.

Spreadability

The formulated polyherbal gel showed good spreadability, indicating easy application and uniform distribution on the skin surface.

consistency

The formulated polyherbal gel showed smooth and homogeneous consistency with good appearance and ease of application.

CONCLUSION

The formulated polyherbal anti-inflammatory gel containing *Moringa oleifera* and *Curcuma longa* was successfully prepared using a suitable gel base and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters. The results of the evaluation studies such as pH, homogeneity, viscosity, spreadability, extrudability, and stability indicated that the formulation possesses acceptable gel characteristics for topical application. The incorporation of phytoconstituents like flavonoids, phenols, and curcuminoids contributes to the potential anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity of the formulation. Overall, the developed polyherbal gel can be considered a promising, safe, and effective topical herbal formulation for the management of inflammation, with scope for further in vitro and in vivo pharmacological studies.

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